

Nwulite Obodo Open Data License (NOODL)

Plain-Language Explainer

This Explainer communicates the key principles of the Nwulite Obodo Open Data License (Version 1.0), in accessible language, while preserving the core legal elements from the full licence.

Nwulite Obodo Open Data License (Version 1.0) — Summary

1. What is this licence?

The **Nwulite Obodo Open Data License** (also known as “NOODL”) is an open data licence created to support fair and community-centred sharing of African datasets. It builds on the principles of Creative Commons but adds special considerations to ensure equitable use, *especially between users inside and outside Africa* and other developing regions

2. Who is this for?

- **Dataset Providers:** People or organisations creating or owning the dataset.
- **Data Recipients:** Anyone who accesses or uses the dataset, from Africa, other developing countries, or elsewhere.

The licence sets different terms depending on where the recipient is based.

3. Key freedoms for recipients in Africa & developing countries

If you're a recipient from Africa or another developing country, you are granted a **worldwide, royalty-free, non-exclusive, irrevocable right** to:

- Use the dataset.
- Adapt or remix it.
- Share it **within** developing countries—under **the same licence**.
- Engage in **commercial use**, but only **outside** Africa/developing countries.

4. Key requirements for recipients outside Africa/developing countries

If you're based **outside** Africa or other developing countries:

- You may use or adapt the dataset **only** under the same licence terms.
- You must provide a **benefit (that could include royalties)** to the original Dataset Provider (e.g., monetary payment, partnership, other agreed benefits).
- You may then share adapted data back to Africa or other recipients under the same licence **provided that** you respect the licensing terms.

5. Common obligations for all recipients

- **Attribution:** Give credit to the Dataset Provider(s) as provided (e.g., names, copyright notice, link to licence).
- **Share-Alike:** If you adapt the dataset, you must license your version under this same licence.
- **No additional restrictions:** Do not impose further limitations (e.g., technological protection, DRM).
- **Respect moral rights:** The Dataset Provider retains moral rights.

6. Warranties and liability

The data is provided “**as-is**”, with **no warranties** regarding its accuracy or suitability. The Dataset Provider is **not liable** for any damages caused by its use.

7. When does the licence apply, and when does it end?

- The licence begins when the data is made available.
- It remains valid **as long as** recipients continue to follow its terms.
- If a recipient fails to comply, the licence rights end automatically—but may be **restored** if they correct the issue within 30 days.
- In addition, the licence may **terminate or adjust** if a country's development status changes, including a five-year adjustment period.

8. Tool for transparency: The “Split Sheet”

Before applying the licence to their work, providers are encouraged to use an “**African Dataset Creation Split Sheet**”; a document that records contributors, roles, and percentage contributions. This enhances transparency and supports fair attribution and benefit-sharing.

Summary of Licence Conditions

Term	Recipients in Africa/ Developing Countries		Recipients outside these regions	
Use & share	Worldwide & royalty-free	✓	With paybacks	✓
Adapt/remix	Yes	✓	Yes	✓
Commercial use	Inside developing countries; outside <i>with benefit-sharing</i>	✓	Permitted <i>with benefits to the Data Providers</i>	✓
Share-Alike	Required	✓	Required	✓
Attribution	Yes	✓	Yes	✓
No additional restrictions	Yes	✓	Yes	✓

Why this licence matters

Nwulite Obodo means “building community”—this licence empowers African dataset creators and communities by:

- Recognises the curation and preservation of cultural data by communities.
- Promoting fairness and cultural recognition.
- Preventing exploitative extraction of data by wealthy global actors.
- Ensuring any benefits from non-local use return to African communities.

Learn more & contribute

This is a **Plain-Language Explainer**. For the full legal text, detailed definitions, and version history, see the full licence at www.licensingafricandatasets.com, or scan the QR code below.

In essence:

Use the data **freely and fairly**, but recognise—and **reward**—the people and communities who created it, especially when you’re outside the community benefiting from it.

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Licensing African datasets

DATA SCIENCE LAW LAB

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